

QUANTIFICATION OF UNCERTAINTIES IN COMPOSITES VIA COMPUTATIONAL SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

A methodology and an attendant computer code are described to computationally simulate the uncertain behavior of composite structures. The uncertain behavior includes buckling loads, stress concentration factors, displacements, stress/strain etc., which are the consequences of the inherent uncertainties (scatter) in the primitive (independent random) variables (constituent, ply, laminate and structural) that describe the composite structures. The computer code is IPACS (Integrated Probabilistic Assessment of Composite Structures). IPACS can handle both composite mechanics and composite structures. Application to probabilistic composite mechanics is illustrated by its uses to evaluate the uncertainties in all the ply and laminate properties. IPACS application to probabilistic structural analysis is illustrated by its use to evaluate the uncertainties in the buckling of a composite plate.

INTRODUCTION

Probabilistic composite mechanics and probabilistic composite structural analysis are formal methods which are used to quantify the scatter that is observed in composite material properties and structural response. The observed scatter in composite material properties is the range of measured values in modulus, strength, thermal expansion coefficient, etc., while that in structural response is the range of measured values for displacement, frequency, buckling load, etc. The formal methods relate the scatter in the observed values to the corresponding scatter in the physical parameters which make up the composite and/or the composite structure. For example, these parameters include constituent material properties, fabrication process variables, structural component geometry, and any other variables which contribute to the composite behavior and/or structural response.

The development of these types of formal methods has been the subject of considerable research at NASA Lewis Research Center for the past 12 years. This research has led to computational simulation methods and attendant computer codes for relating the scatter (uncertainties) in the composite properties or composite structural response to the corresponding uncertainties in the respective parameters (primitive variables) which are used to describe the composite in all its inherent scales: micro, macro, laminate and structural. A more recent continuing development is the computer code IPACS. (Integrated Probabilistic Assessment of Composite Structures) The objective of this paper is to summarize the status of the IPACS and to present results of select examples to illustrate its application to evaluate the uncertainties in composites and in composite structures. The fundamental concepts driving the methodology are briefly described for completeness. The significance and/or relevance of the results obtained to actual design problems are noted.

FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPTS

The fundamental concepts/assumptions in the probabilistic composite mechanics described herein are (1) the scatter in all the primitive variables, which describe the composite, can be represented by well known probabilistic distribution, (2) the values for the primitive variables can be randomly selected from the known distributions for a specific composite, (3) these value can be used in composite mechanics to predict composite behavior, (4) the whole process can be repeated many times to obtain sufficient information to develop the distribution of the ply properties composite properties, or structural responses. These concepts are analogous to making and testing composites. The probabilistic distributions represent available materials that the composite can be made from. The composite mechanics represent the physical experiment and the process repetition represents several experiments. Subsequent statistical analysis of the data is the same for both approaches. The primitive variables which describe the composite are identified by examining the fabrication process. A schematic depicting the fabrication process for an aircraft wing top cover is shown in Fig. 1. Uncertainties associated with those primitive variables are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

PROBABILISTIC COMPOSITE MECHANICS

Probabilistic composite mechanics is key to probabilistic structural analysis. Probabilistic composite mechanics from micromechanics to laminate theory is described in [1]. Briefly it is a combination of composite mechanics and probability concepts. Respective schematics of the computational simulation of the physics are shown in Fig. 2. Representative results from composite micromechanics are shown in Fig. 3 for the ply longitudinal compressive strength. It is interesting to observe from the sensitivity factors that: (1) the fiber volume ratio (FVR), the matrix compressive strength (SMC), the matrix shear modulus (GM) and the fiber misalignment (THETA 15) affect the ply longitudinal compressive strength in that order; (2) the fiber shear modulus and the matrix shear strength have comparatively negligible effect; (3) the single experimental point is near the 80 percent probability; and (4) the level of probability does not affect the magnitude of the sensitivities (0.0001 versus 0.5).

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Representative results of probabilistic laminate behavior simulation are summarized in Table 3 for three different laminates [2]. Scanning the ranges in this Table, it can be observed that the experimental data is within the simulated scatter for all the values except one Poisson's ratio and two shear moduli. Both of which are sensitive to the boundary and loading conditions. The simulation scatter can be modified to include these data point by modeling the specimen in its entirety. Laminate thermal expansion coefficient results are shown in Fig. 4. Just about every primitive variable affects this laminate property except the fiber volume ratio. These sensitivity factors are not affected by probability levels.

PROBABILISTIC STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Probabilistic structural analysis is performed by using IPACS (Integrated Probabilistic Assessment of Composite Structures)[3]. A schematic of the physics integrated into IPACS is shown in Fig. 5. As can be seen in Fig. 6, IPACS consists of a combination of two major modules. (1) NESSUS for probabilistic structural analysis and PIGAN for probabilistic composite mechanics. IPACS is used to evaluate the scatter in a structural component as is described below.

COMPOSITE PLATE BUCKLING

Representative results from applying IPACS to simulate buckling of composite plates are shown in Fig. 6. The most significant point to observe in this figure is that the plates with the asterisk required probabilistic simulation of the support fixity to increase the simulated results upper bound in order to include the experimental values. The fixity of the supports was simulated by assuming a ten percent end-moment and a five percent scatter about this ten percent fixity. The conclusion is that experimental results can be bounded by including uncertainties in all the primitive variables that describe the composite structure and its respective supports.

CONCLUSIONS

Formal methods and a computer code IPACS for integrated probabilistic assessment of composite structures were described. Select examples for probabilistic composite mechanics and probabilistic structural analysis were presented to demonstrate the status of the development of the code and its applications. Results from these examples illustrate that those formal methods can be used to quantify the uncertainties in composite structural behavior from the inherent uncertainties in the various parameters that define the composite structure. In addition, the methodology can be used to evaluate sensitivity factors which influence composite response. Boundary conditions are important in composite plates with certain laminate configurations.

REFERENCES

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2. G. T. Mase, P.L.N.Murthy and C. C. Chamis, Probabilistic micromechanics and macromechanics of polymer matrix composites. NASA TM 103669, January 1991.
3. M. C. Shiao, Abumeri, G. H. and C. C. Chamis, Probabilistic assessment of composite structures. NASA TM 106368, April 1993.

TABLE I. - MATERIAL PROPERTIES AT CONSTITUENT LEVEL FOR BOTH SKIN AND STRINGERS

	Unit	Distribution type	Mean	Coefficient of variation
E_{f11}	Msi	Normal	31.0	0.05 ↓
E_{f22}	Msi	Normal	2.0	
G_{f12}	Msi	Normal	2.0	
G_{f23}	Msi	Normal	1.0	
ν_{f12}	---	Normal	0.2	
ν_{f23}	---	Normal	0.25	
α_{f11}	ppm/°F	Normal	-0.55	
α_{f22}	ppm/°F	Normal	5.6	
ρ_f	lb/in. ³	Normal	0.063	
N_f	---	Constant	10 000	
d_f	in.	Normal	0.0003	
C_f	Btu in./°F	Normal	0.17	
K_{f11}	Btu in./hr/in. ² /°F	Normal	580	
K_{f22}	Btu in./hr/in. ² /°F	Normal	58	
K_{f33}	Btu in./hr/in. ² /°F	Normal	58	
S_{fT}	Ksi	Weibull	400	
S_{fC}	Ksi	Weibull	400	
E_m	Msi	Normal	0.5	
G_m	Msi	Normal	0.185	
ν_m	---	Normal	0.35	
α_m	ppm/°F	Normal	42.8	
ρ_m	lb/in. ³	Normal	0.0443	
C_m	Btu/in./°F	Normal	0.25	
K_{mT}	Btu in./hr/in. ² /°F	Normal	1.25	
S_{mT}	Ksi	Weibull	15	
S_{mC}	Ksi	Weibull	35	
S_{mS}	Ksi	Weibull	13	
β_m	in./in./1% moist	Normal	0.004	
D_m	in. ³ /sec	Normal	0.002	

TABLE II. - FABRICATION VARIABLES
AT PLY LEVEL

	Unit	Distribution type	Mean	Coefficient of variation
fvr	---	Normal ↓	0.60	0.05
vvr	---		.02	.05
θ_p	deg		.00	.9 (stdv)
t_{psk}	in.		.005	.05
t_{pst}	in.		.02	.05

TABLE III. - PIGAN VERIFICATION FOR LAMINATE STIFFNESS

Laminate	Lower bound (95% confidence)	Mean	Experimental value ^a	Upper bound (95% confidence)
$[0/\pm 45_2/0/\pm 45]_s$				
Long. modulus (Msi)	5.48	6.31	6.30	7.12
Trans. modulus (Msi)	2.76	3.16	3.08	3.54
Shear modulus (Msi)	3.34	3.85	3.21	4.38
Major Poisson's ratio	.771	.792	.803	.813
$[0_2/\pm 45/0_2/90/0]_s$				
Long. modulus (Msi)	11.49	13.27	13.00	15.08
Trans. modulus (Msi)	3.85	4.40	4.20	4.93
Shear modulus (Msi)	1.42	1.63	1.50	1.84
Major Poisson's ratio	.305	.312	.325	.318
$[(0/\pm 45/90)_2]_s$				
Long. modulus (Msi)	6.27	7.22	6.68	8.16
Trans. modulus (Msi)	6.27	7.22	6.62	8.16
Shear modulus (Msi)	2.38	2.74	2.34	3.10
Major Poisson's ratio	.310	.315	.350	.320

Figure 1.—Sources of scatter - fabrication process.

Figure 2.—Composite behavior simulation - ICAN.

Figure 3. - Probabilistic ply longitudinal compressive strength (AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy at 0.6 FVR).

Figure 4. - Probabilistic laminate thermal expansion coefficient along the 0° plies ($[0/\pm 45/0\pm 45]_s$, AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite).

Figure 5. - IPACS: Integrated Probabilistic Assessment of Composite Structures

Figure 6. - Probabilistically simulated buckling loads of boron/epoxy composite plates.